

Table 2. Minimum model for each cross.

Parameter	Pokkali/Djabon			Pa Merr 108A/HG90-2		
	Estimate	Standard error	Probability	Estimate	Standard error	Probability
m	= 0.582	0.057	<0.001	0.447	0.016	<0.001
[d]	= 0.105	0.013	<0.001	0.118	0.017	<0.001
[h]	= -0.155	0.075	<0.05			
[i]	= -0.175	0.059	<0.01	-0.064	0.026	<0.05
X ² (3)	= 2.729			X ² (3) = 2.994		
P	= 0.50 - 0.25			P = 0.50 - 0.25		

Table 3. Minimum model in the presence of a maternal effect.

Parameter	Pokkali/Djabon			Pa Merr 108A/BG90-2		
	Estimate	Standard error	Probability	Estimate	Standard error	Probability
m	= 0.418	0.011	<0.001	0.404	0.012	<0.001
[d]	= 0.110	0.013	<0.001	0.113	0.016	<0.001
[hm]	= 0.089	0.028	<0.001	0.077	0.029	<0.05
X ² (3)	= 3.8171			X ² (3) = 1.985		
P	= 0.50 - 0.25			P = 0.75 - 0.50		

presence of a maternal effect (Table 3), three terms – m, [d], and [hm] – emerged as the most important parameters. The highly significant [d] confirmed that the variation observed in the generation means was mainly due to the additive genetic effects for salt tolerance, and [hm] represents the dispersion of the dominant genes determining the maternal effect of the F₁ mothers, which increased

the tolerance of the progenies. In all cases, the X² is insignificant, showing that there are no nonallelic interactions.

The slight bimodal distribution of the F₂ (see figure) with a big peak at 0.40-0.49 TR and a minor peak at 0.80-0.89 TR suggests only a few genes determine salt tolerance. Transgressive segregation toward high tolerance was observed. The broad sense heritability ranged from

Distribution of means of parents, F₁, and F₂ plants. Solid horizontal lines show the range of the parents and F₁ plants about their means.

49.2% in Pokkali/Djabon to 83.3% in Pa Merr 108A/BG90-2, indicating the possibility of early selections of salt-tolerant individuals. □

Soil amendments for sodic conditions

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We evaluated the effect of gypsum, farmyard manure (FYM), and ZnSO₄ application on rice yield on a Ghabdan loam soil (salic Natraqualf) in Sangrur district, Punjab, India. The soil had pH 10.3, 0.07% organic carbon, 1.55% calcium carbonate, 81.9% exchangeable sodium, and 0.43 ppm available Zn. Treatments (see table) were in a randomized block design with three replications. All plots received 120 kg N/ha as urea and 26 kg P/ha as superphosphate. Gypsum, FYM, or ZnSO₄, 40 kg N/ha, and P were broadcast and mixed in the top 15 cm of soil before submergence. Thirty-day-old PR106 rice seedlings were transplanted 1 d after

Effect of gypsum, FYM, and ZnSO₄ on Zn and Na content and grain yield of rice, Ludhiana, India.

Treatment	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)	Grain content		Straw content		pH ^b
		Zn (ppm)	Na(ppm)	Zn (ppm)	Na(%)	
Control	0.1	8	2363	10	2.3	10.0
11.2 kg Zn/ha	0.1	10	2290	15	2.2	9.9
25% soil requirement of gypsum	1.5	9	975	10	1.5	9.2
25% gypsum + 11.2 kg Zn/ha	2.2	12	910	17	1.4	9.0
50% soil requirement of gypsum	2.0	10	585	13	1.0	8.6
50% gypsum + 11.2 kg Zn/ha	3.0	12	495	19	0.9	8.2
15 t FYM/ha	0.4	10	1948	14	2.0	9.7
15 t FYM/ha + 11.2 kg Zn/ha	1.0	11	1832	17	1.9	9.5
LSD at 5%	0.2	0.9	168	0.8	0.09	0.6
<i>Correlation coefficients (r values)</i>						
Grain yield	1.0	0.65**	-0.94**	0.55**	-0.96**	-0.87**

^aOven-dry basis. ^bAfter rice crop harvest, 1:2 soil water suspension. **Significant at P = 0.01.

submergence. Remaining N was top-dressed in 2 equal splits, 21 and 45 d after transplanting.

In the no-treatment plots, rice plants grew poorly or died. Plants that

lived had restricted growth, and severe Zn deficiency and Na toxicity. Applying gypsum significantly increased grain yield and Zn content and decreased Na content in grain and straw (see table).

Gypsum (50% of the gypsum requirement of the soil) plus 11.2 kg Zn/ha produced maximum grain yield. FYM alone or in combination with Zn was inferior even to 25% gypsum alone. □

Varietal differences in P uptake of rice on sodic soils

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We screened salt-tolerant varieties IR54, IR4563-52-1-1-3-6, IR9975-5-1, IR146-32-22-3, IR19661-131-1-2, M242, and Pokkali for P uptake in sodic soils. Cultivars were transplanted in 4 replications in field plots with pH 8.5-8.9, 9.0-9.4, and 9.5-10.0. N, P, and K were applied at 120, 26, and 25 kg/ha as urea, single superphosphate, and muriate of potash. After harvest, grain and straw samples were analyzed for P content (Tables 1 and 2). Pokkali yielded best, followed by IR4563-52-

Table 1. Effect of soil alkalinity on grain yield and straw-to-grain ratio of paddy, Kanpur, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)				Straw:grain			
	pH 8.7	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	Average	pH 8.7	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	Average
IR54	2.5	1.8	0.5	1.6	1.8	2.4	6.4	3.5
IR4563-52-1-1-3-6	4.2	3.7	2.5	3.5	1.2	1.1	1.6	1.3
IR9975-5-1	4.2	2.4	1.7	2.8	1.3	1.7	2.8	1.9
IR14632-22-3	2.6	2.0	2.1	2.3	3.3	3.7	3.8	3.6
IR19661-131-1-2	3.1	2.8	2.2	2.7	2.0	1.9	1.7	1.8
M242	2.4	2.3	2.5	2.4	2.2	1.7	1.9	1.9
Pokkali	4.7	3.6	2.9	3.7	1.8	1.9	1.7	1.8
Average	3.4	2.7	2.1		1.9	2.1	2.8	

Table 2. Effect of soil alkalinity on total P uptake and percentage translocation in grain, Kanpur, India.

Variety	Total P uptake (kg/ha)				% translocation of P in grain			
	pH 8.7	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	Average	pH 8.7	pH 9.2	pH 9.6	Average
IR54	13.2	12.9	8.1	11.4	62.9	40.2	21.8	41.6
IR4563-52-1-1-3-6	22.1	17.9	11.7	17.2	72.3	72.5	58.0	67.6
IR9975-5-1	24.2	14.3	13.3	17.3	67.0	57.1	44.8	56.3
IR14632-22-3	20.1	21.4	18.6	20.3	41.4	32.6	36.9	33.5
IR19661-131-1-2	19.6	16.6	11.7	15.9	56.2	56.3	60.3	51.6
M242	14.4	12.5	13.1	13.3	56.3	55.2	55.3	55.6
Pokkali	26.2	19.0	14.3	19.8	65.3	63.7	65.4	64.8
Average	19.9	16.3	12.9		60.2	53.9	48.6	

1-1-3-6. IR54 yielded least. As pH increased, grain yield and P uptake decreased. Highest yielding varieties had

comparatively higher translocation of P in grains (Table 2). □

Pest management and control DISEASES

A possible source of resistance to rice grassy stunt virus (GSV)

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The occurrence of a new GSV strain (GSV 2) that can overcome the resistance gene to ordinary GSV 1 prompted us to search for new sources of resistance.

A perennial rice plant, Guang-Keng A/*Oryza rufipogon*/*Oryza longistaminata* (IRRI acc. no. 104315), was introduced from China in 1980. Plants were propagated by dividing tillers, and seedlings obtained in a natural set of these plants were tested for GSV 1 and GSV 2 infection (see table). Twenty to 130 viruliferous brown planthoppers (BPH) were allowed inoculation access for 2 to 4 d on the tillers and seedlings. Virus

Reaction of divided tillers and seedlings of Guang-Keng A/*Oryza rufipogon*/*Oryza longistaminata* (acc. no. 104315) to GSV 1 and GSV 2, IIRRI, 1984.^a

Plant part tested	Plant type	Inoculated strain	Insects ^b (no./plants)	Plants (no.)		Virus recovery ^c			
				Inoculated	Infected	Plants (no.)		BPH (no.)	
						Tested ^d	Recovered	Tested	Infective
Tiller		GSV 1	20	18	0	—	—	—	—
		GSV 1	50	4	0	—	—	—	—
		GSV 1	130	4	1	1	0	20	0
		GSV 2	50	21	1	1	0	40	0
Seedling	Dwarf	GSV 1	20	1	1	1	1	16	1
		GSV 1	120	2	2	2	1	80	1
	Tall	GSV 1	20	3	1	1	0	17	0
		GSV 1	120	1	0	—	—	—	—
	Dwarf	GSV 2	25	9	9	—	—	—	—
		GSV 2	120	1	1	1	1	40	1
		GSV 2	20	4	3	2	1	123	1
		GSV 2	25	5	1	—	—	—	—
	Tall	GSV 2	120	2	0	—	—	—	—

^aInoculation was done 2 or 4 wk after sowing. ^b2 to 4 d inoculation access period. ^cDone at various times (15–210 d) after inoculation. ^dOnly infected plants were tested.

recovery tests were conducted on inoculated plants using virus-free BPH and the latex test confirmed the presence or

absence of the virus.

None of the 22 tillers inoculated with GSV 1 at 20 or 50 insects/tiller was